

Taiyi sheng shui 太一生水

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The Taiyi sheng shui 太一生水 is a fourth century BCE Chu 楚 manuscript written on 14 bamboo slips, discovered in 1993 in the archaeological excavation of the Guodian 郭店 tomb n.1, in Jingmen 荊門, Hubei 湖北 province. It has been given the title Taiyi sheng shui by the editors of the Guodian Chu mu zhujian 郭店楚墓竹簡, based on the first four characters written on what is deemed to be the first strip. The text, written in the Chu script, appears to be divided into two main halves, and the debate is still open as to whether they represent two sections of a consistent text or two separate documents. The first half describes a cosmological cycle that begins with Taiyi making water alive and ends with the the completion of a yearly cycle, through a process of reciprocal assistance by a series of dyadic couples (the sky and the earth, shen 神 and ming 明, yin and yang, the four seasons, cold and warmth, wetness and dryness); the second half deals with various topics: the workings of the tiandao 天道 (way of the sky); the different designations assigned to Taiyi 太一, the “Great One”, whose names, ming 名, are qing 清 (bright) and hun 昏 (dark), and whose honorific, zi 字, is dao 道 (way); the services performed by the sage and by the people, who both need to rely on the names of Taiyi; the tilt that occurred between the sky and earth, whereby the sky is insufficient in the north-west, while the earth is insufficient in the south-east (a recurring account on the asset of the sky and the earth in Chu texts, e.g. Tianwen 天問). The Taiyi sheng shui appears to share the same material carrier with one of the three Laozi 老子 manuscripts found in the same tomb, the Guodian Laozi C 郭店老子丙, and for this reason the majority of scholarly works hypothesize a correspondence of Taiyi to the Laozian dao. This supposed connection between the two texts led to an understanding of the first half of the Taiyi sheng shui as a cosmogony connected to the cosmogonic chapters of the Daodejing 道德經 (ch. 25;42), despite the process ending with the completion of the year (cheng sui 成歲) rather than with the coming into being of material reality. Within this framework, Taiyi in this text has been understood as a name for the dao (Allan 2003; Cook 2012; Brindley 2019; Wang 2016), as the homonymous god known from Han religious cults (Harper 2001), as a name for the pole star and its god (Allan 2003). A recent study (Puglia 2021) reads the two halves of the manuscript as a consistent whole, in which Taiyi is a name for the sun that apparently moves along with the seasons in the sky, marking the completion of the year, and tracing the tiandao that people should understand in order to act timely and get accomplishments done. The identification of Taiyi with the sun in this manuscript is based on the detailed description of its movements provided in the text. It is said to proceed with the seasons (行於時), to make a cycle and begin anew (周而又始), and to hide in water (藏於水): the employment of the verbs xing 行 and zhou 周, typically used to define the sun’s motion in astronomical pre-Qin and early imperial accounts (e.g. Lüshi Chunqiu 呂氏春秋, Huainanzi 淮南子, etc.) recalls the completion of the yearly cycle as the end of the cosmology described in the first half of the manuscript; the hiding in water, on the other hand, parallels the topos of the sun disappearing in water at sunset in the Chu tradition (e.g. Tianwen 天問). Also the names qing and hun given to Taiyi, following Donald Harper’s reading of the same characters in the Mawangdui 馬王堆 medical text entitled Quegu Shiqi 卻鼓食氣, indicate dawn and dusk (Harper 2001), while its honorific dao might refer to the sun’s ecliptic, the huangdao 黃道 (simply referred to as dao in other pre-imperial sources, such as the Lüshi Chunqiu). Taiyi is also defined as the mother of the ten thousand things (萬物母): if Taiyi is the sun, this passage would refer to its essential function of ensuring the conditions for the existence and reproduction of things on earth, providing light and heat, and driving the water cycle (also explaining the fundamental role of shui 水, water, in the manuscript). Taiyi is finally said to weave making the warp of the ten thousand things (以紀為萬物經): the sun was traditionally taken both as a spatial and as a temporal benchmark for all things on earth, based on the directions of its rising and setting and on the regularity of

its yearly cycle. According to this reading, the two halves of the text are consistent with each other: the first half provides a clarification of the various steps which cooperate for the completion of the year, which is marked by the apparent revolution of the sun in the sky. This revolution of the sun recalls the tiandao of the second half of the text, on which people should base their activities.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Jingmen, Hubei Province, China

Region tags: China, Hebei, Jiang Han Region, Chu, Jingmen

The heartland of Chu Kingdom (ca. 1050-223 BCE) in the 4th century BCE.

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館 (ed.). 1998. Guodian Chu mu zhujian 郭店楚墓竹簡. Peking: Wenwu Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://zh.wikisource.org/wiki/郭店楚墓竹簡#太一生水>
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&chapter=318232>
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.colorado.edu/faculty/richter-matthias/database>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://zh.wikisource.org/wiki/郭店楚墓竹簡#太一生水>
- Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=gb&chapter=318232>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Notes: The Taiyi sheng shui 太一生水 is written on 14 bamboo slips. A few slips are broken or corrupted, causing the presence of major lacunae in the text. Size of the slips: L 26,5; W 0,4-0,65. Total number of graphs: 304.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field does not know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field does not know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The manuscript is stored in the Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館 (Museum of the city of Jingmen).

↳ Tomb

– Yes

Notes: The text has been excavated from Guodian 郭店 tomb n.1 in Jingmen 荊門, Hubei, after the tomb had been robbed.

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

- ↳ Devotional marker
 - No
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館 (Museum of the city of Jingmen)

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text was probably part of the private collection of the owner of the tomb in which it had been buried together with other 17 manuscripts. According to Li Boqian, the owner was an old man, possibly the tutor of a Chu prince. But there is not enough evidence for a precise identification. The variety in the material carrier of the texts, in the content, and in the calligraphic style suggest that the texts were not specifically compiled for the burial.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Taiyi sheng shui is part of the Guodian corpus of bamboo manuscripts found in Guodian tomb n.1. Scholars believe this corpus was (part of) a private collection, propriety of the tomb owner.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars (e.g. S. Allan, S. Scott, E. Brindley, Z. Wang) believe the text pertains to the Daoist

textual tradition, but the topic is controversial.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The manuscript does not formulate a religious calendar, nevertheless, when Taiyi is taken as a name for the sun, the focus on the cyclical sequence of days, seasons, and years in the text is evident. The first six bamboo slips of the Taiyi sheng shui are focused on a series of steps that define a cosmological cycle. The last step, the one that brings the process to its culmination, is the completion of the year after which the cycle begins anew: 濕燥復相輔也，成歲而止 (3.21–4.2), “wetness and dryness repeatedly assist each other, completing the year (harvest), and bringing (the process) to a halt.” The character employed for “year” here is sui 歲, which means both “year” and “harvest” and directly recalls the apparent cycle of the sun in the sky, starting its journey again after the completion of one year; but also of course, the agricultural year, which culminates in a harvest. The idea of the sun bringing the year to completion is not new to classical Chinese texts. One of many examples can be found in the Tianwen 天文 chapter of the Huainanzi 淮南子, which explains the yearly solar cycle: 日行一度，以周於天，日冬至峻狼之山，日移一度，凡行百八十二度八分度之五，而夏至牛首之山，反覆三百六十五度四分度之一而成一歲, “the sun proceeds one du to cycle around the sky. At the winter solstice, the sun is in the High Wolf Mountain. It shifts one du each day, it approximately proceeds 182 du and 5/8 and, at the summer solstice, it is in the Ox Head Mountain. It cycles and with 365 du and a quarter completes one year.” The motion verbs used of the sun in this passage from the Huainanzi are the same verbs used of Taiyi in the Taiyi sheng shui, the verb xing 行 (to proceed) and the verb zhou 周 (to cycle, to make a circle). Taiyi is said to proceed with the seasons (行於時) and to make a cycle and begin anew (周而又始), marking both the sequence of the four seasons and the end/beginning of the year. Taiyi is also said to hide in water (藏於水): this seems to be more plausibly related to its daily motion. The sun in fact apparently disappears in water daily when it sets. This image recalls the traditional conception of the geography of the tianxia 天下, as it emerges for example from the Shanhai jing 山海經, according to which the central land is surrounded by the four seas. This conception appears to be the basis of accounts about the nocturnal journey of the sun related to water, as they appear, for example, in the Chuci Tianwen 楚辭天問 (in a passage also recalled in the Huainanzi, chapter Tianwen): 出自湯谷次於蒙汜，自明及晦所行幾裡, “it rises from the Gorge of Boiling Water and it rests in the River of Obscurity. From light to dark, how many li is its path long?”. Sunrise and sunset are also recalled by the choice of the names, ming 名, associated to Taiyi in the text, that are qing 清 and hun 昏: if we follow Harper’s translation of the same characters in the Mawangdui 馬王堆 medical text Quegu Shiqi 卻鼓食氣, they assume the clear meaning of “dawn” and “dusk”. Furthermore, an alternative reading for the opening

line (and title) of the manuscript has been proposed by Chen, presupposing the omission of the preposition *yu* 於, either purposeful or not (Chen 2000). In such case, the line would read “Taiyi comes forth from water,” hinting to sunrise.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The terms *Taiyi* 太一 and *shen ming* 神明 can refer to supernatural beings. *Taiyi* 太一: Donald Harper identifies *Taiyi* in the *Taiyi sheng shui* with a numinous entity related to the homonymous Han dynasty deity, whose cults are deemed to have roots in Warring States common religion. Sarah Allan hypothesizes a possible understanding of *Taiyi* as a god or spirit related to the pole star. *Shen ming* 神明: According to Knoblock, the term *shen ming* in Warring States texts often refers to divine beings, gods, and spirits. Both Harper and Wang Bo identify *shen ming* as a religious concept. According to Small, the compound *shenming* originally referred to two types of gods, atmospheric and stellar, and

then the term extended to indicate all kinds of gods in general, and later the marvelous functions of the dao. Beyond the religious reading of the two characters as a compound, their significance as single characters with opposite and complementary connotations (as the other dyadic couples involved in the cosmological process of the Taiyi sheng shui) can be traced to the primary meaning of ming as something related to light or something that makes sight possible, and to the origins of the character shen deriving from shen 申 (rod), and therefore from the early pictograph for "lightning" (lei 電), connected to cloudy weather and night. Therefore, while ming can be understood in its basic acceptation of light and visibility, shen (which seems also to appear as a synonym for characters indicating darkness such as you 幽, an 暗, hui 晦, and ming 冥) can be intended as something outshining light, such as clouds darkening the sun on a stormy day, or the moon covering the sun during an eclipse, or things obstructing light and casting shadows.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Field doesn't know

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The cosmology described in the Taiyi sheng shui might be possibly related, as hypothesized by Allan, to a divination tool known as shi 式 (cosmograph or diviner's board). Allan claims that the cosmograph provided a set of images, a round sky with a central pivot mounted on a square earth, that influenced the perception of the world and presented an idealized cosmology concerned with temporal change. According to Allan's reading, the connection between the text and the cosmograph serves to prove the identification of Taiyi with the pole star, which represents the unmovable apex of the sky vault and therefore of the round sky-disc of the divination tool. The connection with the cosmograph might still hold even when we identify Taiyi with the sun: In fact, the twelve numbers that usually appear written on the sky-disc of the shi serve to indicate the lodge in which the sun is expected to be found in a given month, thereby providing a schematized model of the basic time sequences of the cosmos.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - No
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - No
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - No
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - No
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No

- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: The text refers to the sheng ren 聖人 (sage person) as the one who relies on Taiyi's name in carrying out his services, completing achievements and avoiding harm. The text also refers to the junzi 君子 (gentleman) as one who has knowledge about the cosmological process described in the first half of the manuscript. Unfortunately, the bamboo strip is corrupted at its end, therefore the last characters of the sentence are lost.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The Taiyi sheng shui was produced around 300 BCE, during the Warring States era, in the state of Chu 楚.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None that the field knows about.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education had been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text does not directly mention food production, nevertheless it appears to be possibly related to agriculture. It both emphasizes the central role of water in bringing to completion the sky (in a mainly agricultural society, rain and fresh water are fundamental to achieving a successful harvest) and lists a series of climatic and seasonal conditions that appear to be strictly related to the management of the annual harvest (e.g. cold and warmth and wetness and dryness) and that are all obviously related to the path of the sun in the sky.

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